

A Study of Comparative Teacher-freezing of Higher Education Teachers working in Rural and Urban Areas

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Abstract

The present study was intended to investigate the teacher-freezing of higher education teachers in context of locality (rural and urban) of their institutions. The objective of the study was to compare the teacher-freezing of rural and urban area higher education teachers on each dimension of teacher-freezing and their overall freezing. A total of 160 higher education teachers with 80 rural and 80 urban degree college teachers were selected randomly from various higher education institutions of Varanasi region, Uttar Pradesh, for the study. Teacher-freezing Scale (TFS) developed by Dr Haseen Taj (1996) was administered on the samples to assess teacher-freezing. Shapiro-Wilk test was applied to check the normality of data sets and CR-test was applied to find out the significance of difference between mean freezing scores of the two. Findings of the study revealed that rural and urban area higher education teachers show approximately the same level of teacher-freezing overall. No significant differences were found between them on Intellectual, Psychological, Social and Physical dimensions of teacher-freezing. They differ only on Moral-dimension of teacher-freezing. Urban area college teachers were found more freeze in comparison to rural area college teachers on Moral-dimension of teacher-freezing.

Keywords

Teacher-freezing, Higher education, Rural and urban areas, Lethargy, Apathy

1. INTRODUCTION

Higher education plays a key role in the development of individual, society and nation. It empowers individuals through personal development, career advancement and improved quality of life. It helps in developing more equitable society by promoting social mobility. Higher education stimulates the economic growth of the country by providing specialized knowledge and skilled manpower.

India has one of the largest higher education system in the world. According to AISHE:2021-22 report, there are 1168 universities, 45473 colleges and 12002 stand alone institutions in which 1.6 million teachers and 43.27 million students are engaged. A teacher occupies a unique place in the entire system of education. Being on such a crucial position, his sensitivity and dedication to his work becomes imperative (Becker, 1960) . An effective teacher is one who can take care of the responsibility for planning, guiding and evaluating education system. He is an individual with good cultural values and who believes that his job is essential for the progress of community and the nation at large (Pastariya, 2018) . Today's world is enveloped by an intense advancement of technology which has also affected the process of teaching, learning and thinking. Now the role of a teacher is expected to be quite different from what it was in traditional classroom. A teacher is now required to be more agile in his approach (Symond, 1956) .

Quality is the key feature of higher education. A country can not attain it's goals without providing quality higher education. A teacher has to shoulder this responsibility. Indian government has introduced many policies and programmes to promote professional advancement in higher education teachers but they seem ineffective. In present scenario, teacher's lethargy, apathy and indifferent attitude are the major causes for the deteriorating standards of education today. Lack of interest and enthusiasm of teachers in performing their duties and their inability to innovate in psychological, social, physical and moral aspects is reflected in their working. Of course they seem to freeze.

Many studies have specific concern on teacher-freezing. Pandey & Dwivedi (2010) found maximum financed and non financed secondary school teachers freeze in the study. Basu & Banerjee (2018) explored the factors behind teacher's lethargy, apathy and depersonalization towards teaching profession. They reported that the key factors responsible for freezing proneness are degrading and disquieting attitude towards teaching, depersonalization, emotional exhaustion , autocratic leadership by superiors, lack of interest in teaching work, absence of change proneness, external locus of control, feeling of job monotony, pessimistic attitude, absence of pedagogical knowledge and lack of interest towards societal welfare, indifferent attitude towards others, considering teaching as a last resort of professional choice etc. Many studies tried to investigate teach-freezing with some other variables such as teacher attitude, organizational climate, job satisfaction etc. Sharma, Monika (2013) found a negative significant correlation between teacher Attitude and teacher freezing. She reported that teachers having favourable attitudes possess significantly lower level of teacher freezing as compared to teachers having unfavourable teacher attitude. Hitaishi, Vandana (2014) found significant relationship between teacher freezing and various components of organizational climate. Malik, Umendra (2020) reported that teachers having high job satisfaction have less degree of teacher freezing.

Studies related to Teacher-freezing are associated mostly with secondary school teachers. There is a lack of studies on freezing of higher education teachers. So, investigator decided to explore it with higher education teachers.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

As per the nature of the study, descriptive survey method was applied to investigate freezing behaviour of higher education teachers of Varanasi region. A total of 160 (80 from rural areas and 80 from urban areas) degree college teachers were selected through stratified random sampling method. A standardized tool 'Teacher Freezing Scale' developed by Dr. Haseen Taj (1996), department of Education, Bengaluru University, was used to assess the teacher-freezing of rural and urban areas degree college teachers. Shapiro-Wilk test was applied on the data set to ensure the normality of data gathered. As distribution was found normal and interval scale of assessment was used, researcher decided to apply CR-test to check whether the difference between the mean freezing scores of rural and urban areas degree college teachers is significant. Researcher decided .05 level of significance for statistical analysis.

3. COMPARISON OF OVERALL TEACHER-FREEZING OF RURAL AND URBAN AREA HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS

Objective 1: To compare overall teacher-freezing of rural and urban area higher education teachers.

H₀1: There is no significant difference between the overall mean freezing scores of rural and urban area higher education teachers.

Table-1

Si. No.	Locality	N	M	SD	CR(Estimated)	CR(Critical)
1	Rural	80	244.80	21.30	0.57	1.98 (0.05 level of significance)
2	Urban	80	246.75	21.81		

Result: Insignificant

It is evident from table-1 that the estimated CR-value 0.57 was found insignificant at 0.05 level which indicates that there is no significant difference between the overall mean freezing scores of rural and urban area higher education teachers.

4. COMPARISON OF TEACHER-FREEZING OF RURAL AND URBAN AREA HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS ON INTELLECTUAL-FREEZING DIMENSION

Objective 2: To compare teacher-freezing of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Intellectual-freezing dimension.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between mean freezing scores of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Intellectual-freezing dimension.

Table-2

Si. No.	Locality	N	M	SD	CR(Estimated)	CR(Critical)
1	Rural	80	82.05	5.16	0.29	1.98 (0.05 level of significance)
2	Urban	80	81.81	5.21		

Result: Insignificant

It is evident from table-2 that the estimated CR-value 0.29 was found Insignificant at 0.05 level of significance which indicates that there is no significant difference between mean freezing scores of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Intellectual dimension of teacher-freezing.

5. COMPARISON OF RURAL AND URBAN AREA HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS ON PSYCHOLOGICAL-FREEZING DIMENSION

Objective 3: To compare teacher-freezing of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Psychological-freezing dimension.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between mean freezing scores of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Psychological-freezing dimension.

Table-3

Si. No.	Locality	N	M	SD	CR(Estimated)	CR(Critical)
1	Rural	80	45.82	6.39	1.48	1.98 (0.05 level of significance)
2	Urban	80	47.31	6.33		

Result: Insignificant

It is evident from table-3 that the estimated CR-value 1.48 was found Insignificant at 0.05 level of significance which indicates that there is no significant difference between mean freezing scores of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Psychological dimension of teacher-freezing.

6. COMPARISON OF RURAL AND URBAN AREA HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS ON SOCIAL-FREEZING DIMENSION

Objective 4: To compare teacher-freezing of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Social-freezing dimension.

H₀4: There is no significant difference between mean freezing scores of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Social-freezing dimension.

Table-4

Sl. No.	Locality	N	M	SD	CR(Estimated)	CR(Critical)
1	Rural	80	39.15	0.49	1.50	1.98 (0.05 level of significance)
2	Urban	80	40.25	0.54		

Result: Insignificant

It is evident from table-4 that the estimated CR-value 1.50 was found Insignificant at 0.05 level of significance which indicates that there is no significant difference between mean freezing scores of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Social dimension of teacher-freezing.

7. COMPARISON OF RURAL AND URBAN AREA HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS ON PHYSICAL-FREEZING DIMENSION

Objective 5: To compare teacher-freezing of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Physical-freezing dimension.

H₀5: There is no significant difference between mean freezing scores of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Physical-freezing dimension.

Table-5

Si. No.	Locality	N	M	SD	CR(Estimated)	CR(Critical)
1	Rural	80	58.85	5.58	1.21	1.98 (0.05 level of significance)
2	Urban	80	59.92	5.64		

Result: Insignificant

It is evident from table-5 that the estimated CR-value 1.21 was found Insignificant at 0.05 level of significance which indicates that there is no significant difference between mean freezing scores of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Physical dimension of teacher-freezing.

8. COMPARISON OF RURAL AND URBAN AREA HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS ON MORAL-FREEZING DIMENSION

Objective 6: To compare teacher-freezing of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Moral-freezing dimension.

H₀6: There is no significant difference between mean freezing scores of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Moral-freezing dimension.

Table-6

Si. No.	Locality	N	M	SD	CR(Estimated)	CR(Critical)
1	Rural	80	18.90	2.42	3.75	1.98 (0.05 level of significance)
2	Urban	80	17.55	2.13		

Result: Significant

It is evident from table-6 that the estimated CR-value 3.75 was found significant at 0.05 level of significance which indicates that there is a significant difference between mean freezing scores of rural and urban area higher education teachers on Moral dimension of teacher-freezing. Higher education teachers working in urban areas were found more freeze in comparison to higher education teachers working in rural areas.

9. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

Rural and urban area college teachers show approximately the same level of teacher-freezing on Intellectual, Psychological, Social and Physical dimensions. Urban area college teachers were found more freeze in promoting moral values among students in comparison to rural area college teachers. Administration and management of urban area colleges should pay proper attention to practice moral ethics.

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